

Introducing a Prototype of the Goal and Dream Search Engine (SearchGAEP)

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We are excited to introduce the world's first goal and dream search engine, SearchGAEP, and invite users to provide feedback as we explore its strengths and weaknesses. During this research preview, usage of the goal search engine is free. Join our waitlist to gain early access and try it out.

In a world where individuals and organizations are constantly striving to turn their aspirations into reality, achieving personal or professional goals can be a daunting challenge. Balancing competing priorities, managing complexity, adapting to rapid change, and aligning people and resources are just a few key hurdles [1]. Choosing the right pathways is crucial for success. We are testing SearchGAEP, a first-of-its-kind prototype designed to revolutionize how people and organizations approach goal achievement. The goal and dream search engine helps users identify suitable pathways to their goals, integrating various elements such as products, services, opportunities, resources, media, financial transactions, support systems, and methods that contribute to goal accomplishment [2].

A New Way to Search

Achieving goals often requires significant time, effort, and expense, with multiple attempts needed to gather relevant results. Users typically rely on different sources to find information, buy or sell products and services, apply for opportunities, manage daily tasks, obtain financial resources, and more. We believe the goal search engine can streamline this process by providing all these elements in one centralized interface, offering real-time information that makes finding what you need faster and easier.

SearchGAEP represents a revolutionary shift in how people approach their aspirations. For decades, search engines have been essential tools for discovering content. Now, with the power of executive AI, we're enhancing this experience by offering personalized executive paths for goal achievement in an easy-to-use interface, with numerous opportunities for user engagement.

Instead of spending excessive time searching for information via different search engines or creating content via generative AI models, the goal search engine allows users to explore multiple executive pathways to achieve their goals and dreams directly. It provides an efficient, centralized approach to goal attainment through advanced indexing, ranking, and retrieval algorithms that ensure relevant and accurate results. Integrated within an all-in-one platform, the goal search engine offers seamless navigation and connectivity. Using SearchGAEP will help you reduce the time and effort needed to find resources, experts, and information, simplifying the goal achievement process by eliminating the need to search across multiple sources.

A New Method to Manage

For decades, people and organizations have relied on traditional, separate systems to manage their tasks and goals [3]. These include task management tools, project management software, financial systems, time management platforms, and workflow automation tools. However, these systems are often not integrated with one another, nor are they connected with marketplaces for products and services, platforms for opportunities, resources and training, social networks, and more. Additionally, people and organizations may seek personal coaching or hire experts, which can be time-consuming and costly. These approaches sometimes lead to ineffective outcomes because they aren't personalized. Despite these methods, many individuals and organizations continue to struggle with turning their aspirations into tangible results. Current solutions often fail to address the complexities of goal achievement, such as the need for personalized guidance, access to relevant resources, real-time management, and the ability to adapt to changing circumstances.

SearchGAEP helps users improve goal achievement rates, boost productivity and efficiency, and make positive strides in both personal and professional development. The integration of a "super app" within SearchGAEP allows users to manage tasks, track progress, and maintain accountability, all within a single platform. It also enables users to manage time, finances, communication channels, teams, and all other aspects of their goal paths while monitoring progress in real time. Integrated with a comprehensive system, SearchGAEP provides the necessary structure and processes to manage tasks effectively and track progress. The results page offers clear visibility into the status of each task, enabling users to monitor their own progress as well as that of their teammates. By consolidating all

necessary tools and resources, SearchGAEP reduces the time and effort required to make progress, enabling users to focus on taking action toward their objectives.

The platform facilitates efficient task allocation, progress tracking, and collaboration, resulting in better goal management and increased productivity. Users of SearchGAEP experience significantly higher goal achievement rates compared to traditional goal-setting and management methods. This improvement can be attributed to streamlined processes, access to key resources, and continuous support provided by SearchGAEP.

Designed to Improve Goal Achievement Rates

SearchGAEP provides users with personalized pathways to achieve their goals and dreams, incorporating essential elements such as products, services, opportunities, resources, media, financial transactions, support, people, and methods that contribute to success. The ability to customize goal paths and monitor progress empowers individuals to take an active, informed role in achieving their aspirations.

SearchGAEP quickly responds to goal queries with up-to-date information and clear links to relevant resources. Acting like a human expert, it helps users find the most efficient and cost-effective ways to achieve their goals. It assists users at each step of their goal path, serving as a personalized assistant that connects them with the right people, gathers everything they need, and manages all necessary actions at the right time. Users simply need to take the required steps when prompted. The personalized pathways and recommendations provided by SearchGAEP have helped users navigate the complexities of goal achievement, resulting in higher success rates.

Developed to Increase Income

SearchGAEP facilitates financial transactions and provides opportunities for users to save and earn money while pursuing their goals. Users can access funding sources, find cost-effective resources, and discover revenue-generating opportunities through the network, leading to financial benefits. SearchGAEP's ability to connect users with the right products, services, and resources has resulted in cost savings and reduced the time needed to achieve goals. By optimizing the goal achievement process, the system helps users avoid unnecessary expenses and delays, making the pursuit of their aspirations more financially and temporally efficient.

Methods

SearchGAEP, or "Search Engine for Goal Achievement Executive Pathways," is a search engine designed to help individuals find specific, actionable steps (or "pathways") to achieve their goals and dreams. The term "search engine" implies that users can input their goals or dreams and receive curated results or strategies on how to achieve them, focusing on "executive pathways," which represent high-level, effective, or structured methods for success. SearchGAEP combines the power of executive AI models with a comprehensive platform (Super App) to deliver fast, timely executive paths with clear, relevant, and trusted sources. It simplifies the goal achievement process through a three-step approach:

The Goal Achievement Process Through a Three-Step Approach

1. Search:

Users search for their desired goals and dreams within SearchGAEP, exploring a vast database of curated goal-achievement executive pathways. They select the pathway that best aligns with their needs and preferences. Each pathway includes a curated selection of:

- **Products:** Digital and physical products users may need.
- **Services:** Freelance, business, or other services relevant to a specific goal.
- **Opportunities:** Scholarships, grants, jobs, or networking events aligned with users' aspirations.
- **Training:** Inspirational stories, tutorials, courses, programs, or educational content to guide users.
- **Media:** Images, albums, videos, playlists relevant to users' specific goals.
- **Financial Transactions:** Secure platforms for conducting transactions related to users' goals, such as sending, receiving, or requesting funds.
- **Resources:** Online tools, AI tools, news, publications, and other resources relevant to users' specific goals.
- **Support:** Access to mentors, coaches, or communities for encouragement and guidance.
- **People:** Experts and collaborators who can contribute to users' success.
- **Methods:** Detailed action plans with defined steps to achieve the goals.

The search results page of executive pathways displays financial information such as the user's current balance, the cost of goal achievement (if required), and the estimated balance after reaching the goal. It also shows the time users need to spend and work on their goals,

along with the timeframe from the start to the goal's completion. Each page includes information about the executive path, such as expected risk level (from very low to very high), success rate percentage, difficulty level (very easy to very hard), and the number of steps required to achieve the goal or dream.

2. Approve:

Users can make SearchGAEP display the best personalized executive pathway, or they can directly select one of the executive pathways that best aligns with their needs by clicking the "Do it" button.

3. Achieve:

With the support of the all-in-one platform (Super App), SearchGAEP will automatically buy or sell products and services, fill out application forms, apply for opportunities, handle financial transactions (sending or receiving money), connect users with people and partners who can assist them, gather all information and resources related to the goal query, and remind users to take necessary actions to work effectively toward accomplishing their goals.

We are excited to apply the lessons from this release to future deployments of more advanced systems, just as earlier iterations informed this one.

Samples

Example: Scholarship

- **User:** How to find and apply for an international scholarship.
- **SearchGAEP:**

The screenshot displays the SearchGAEP interface for a scholarship application. At the top left is the Ferct logo with a 'Beta' tag and a menu icon labeled 'All'. On the top right are navigation icons for home, refresh, messages, notifications, and a profile icon. A vertical sidebar on the left contains icons for home, refresh, search, messages, profile, location, and a smiley face. The main content area is titled 'Apply for Erasmus Scholarship' and contains the following details:

Steps No: 6	Success rate: : 60%
Risk level: Low	Path Type: Paid
Success rate: : 60%	Cost required: \$300.00
Difficulty level: : Easy	Financial benefits: €9,000.00
Time frame: 3 weeks	Current balance: \$2,000.00
Time required: 20 Horus	Estimated balance: \$11,500.00

Below the table is a section titled 'Erasmus Mundus: A Gateway to Global Education and Cultural Exchange' with the text: 'In today's interconnected world, higher education is no longer bound by geographical borders. Students are increasingly seeking'.

To the right of the main content is a 'Key Steps to Achieving Your Goal' section with a vertical list of six steps, each with a blue circle icon and a trash icon:

- Select the Erasmus Mundus Scholarship
- Take a scholarship course
- Hire a scholarship freelance writer
- Connect with a scholarship Advisor
- Apply for a Scholarship - Erasmus
- Get Scholarship Results

At the bottom of this section is a green button labeled 'Do it'.

Challenges and Future Improvements

While SearchGAEP has shown promising results, there are still areas for improvement. Ongoing user feedback and data analysis will guide further enhancements, such as improving the accuracy and relevance of search results, enhancing collaboration and task-delegation features, and exploring better integration with external platforms and services. We also plan to gather feedback on the prototype from users to bring the best of the experience into Ferct. Although this prototype is temporary, we plan to integrate its best features directly into Ferct in the future. As SearchGAEP continues to evolve and expand, it promises to be a game-changer in empowering individuals and organizations worldwide to navigate the path from aspiration to achievement, ultimately helping them realize their full potential.

Declaration of competing interest

The author declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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- Ferct, #1 AI-powered goal achievement network, brings products, services, opportunities, training, systems, resources and people, all in one place to save money and time, accomplish your tasks and reach your goals more easily and effectively. For more information: www.ferct.com

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